

(M.aq.)²⁺ species in the corresponding binary complexing systems. Further, the linear plot passes through the origin and the slope is unity showing that the values of $\log K_{ML}^M$ and those of corresponding $\log K_{M\text{phen.L}}^M$ are nearly equal irrespective of the nature of the secondary ligand^{1,2}. The probable structure of the simple and mixed ligand complexes of 3-MSA are given below.

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Determination of Formation Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Be(II) Complexes with Substituted Salicylic Acids

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KHADIKAR and coworkers have carried out extensive work on the complex formation of salicylic acid and substituted salicylic acids^{1,2}. In the present communication, studies on Be(II)

complexes with 5-chloro, 5-amino and 5-sulphosalicylic acids are reported. Bjerrum's method³ has been used to determine formation constants of the complexes. Stoichiometry has been determined conductometrically⁴ and by metal estimation. The formation constants have been determined at 30, 35 and 40 ± 0.1° and thermodynamic parameters ΔF , ΔH and ΔS are also reported. The bonding in the complexes is discussed on the basis of ir spectra.

Experimental

An expanded scale pH meter, Systronic Type 322, with an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit was used for pH measurements. All chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade. Conductance measurements were made with a Philips conductivity bridge employing dip type conductivity cell. All measurements were carried out by using a thermostatic bath at 30, 35 and 40° with an accuracy of ± 0.1° at a constant ionic strength of 0.1 M (NaClO₄). The ir spectra of the isolated complexes and ligands used were recorded on a Perkin Elmer IR spectrophotometer, model 237 (4000-650 cm⁻¹) by KBr disc technique.

Results and Discussion

Application of monovariation method⁴ has clearly indicated the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes of Be(II) with 5-chloro, 5-amino and 5-sulphosalicylic acids. The pH-metric titration of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 (M : L) mixtures show clear inflection at two, four and five equivalents of alkali indicating the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The inflection at five equivalents of alkali for 1 : 3 titration curve is probably due to the presence of excess of ligand. Based on metal estimation of the isolated Be-complexes composition of different complexes is found to be Na₂Be(C₇H₃O₅Cl)₂·2H₂O (Found : Be, 1.87. Calcd. : Be, 2.09%); Na₂Be(C₇H₃O₅N)₂·2H₂O (Found : Be, 2.00. Calcd. : Be, 2.29%) and Na₂Be(C₇H₄O₆S)₂·2H₂O (Found : Be, 1.44. Calcd. : Be, 1.59%).

The values of \bar{n} and pL corresponding to different pH values have been calculated employing Bjerrum's pH titration technique. The formation curves were plotted and analysed to give the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ as recorded in Table 1. The error limit in the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ is found to be ± 0.01 and ± 0.02, respectively. A perusal of Table 1 shows that $\log K_1$ follows the order 5-ASA > 5-Cl.SA > 5-SSA, while $\log K_2$ values 5-Cl.SA > 5-ASA > 5-SSA.

The bigger difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ and the high values of $\log K_1/K_2$ are because of steric hindrance of the linking of the second ligand molecule to small sized Be(II). The negative values of ΔH is a favourable requirement for a stable complex compound. The entropy changes calculated for above complexes have negative values.

The ir spectra of all the Be-complexes studied here show a marked shift in the >C=O stretching frequency of carboxylate group from ~ 1700 cm⁻¹ in ligand to about 1600 cm⁻¹ in complex. This observation provides the evidence of metal oxygen

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Be(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	Temp. °C	log K ₁	log K ₂	-ΔF ₁ (k cal/mole)	-ΔF ₂ (k cal/mole)	-ΔH (k cal/mole)	ΔS e.u.
5-Chloro salicylate	30	11.05	7.35	15.42	10.26	48.05	-107.7
	35	10.60	7.20	15.04	10.21		
	40	9.95	7.10	14.34	10.24		
5-Amino salicylate	30	14.40	6.90	20.10	9.63	21.84	-5.7
	35	14.10	6.00	20.00	8.51		
	40	13.90	6.50	20.04	9.37		
5-Sulpho salicylate	30	9.70	5.90	13.54	8.23	21.84	-27.4
	35	9.40	5.40	10.50	7.66		
	40	9.20	5.20	13.26	7.50		

binding in these complexes⁶. If the structure of

the complexes were ---C=O frequency at about 1720 cm^{-1} in place of carboxylate frequency observed at about 1600 cm^{-1} . The absence of a band near 1720 cm^{-1} indicates that the carboxylate to metal bond is essentially ionic.

The presence of lattice water can only be confirmed by the appearance of band below 500 cm^{-1} . Because of the instrumental range used we could not confirm the presence of lattice water. However, the absence of a band at 800 cm^{-1} , which is observed in all the complexes in which water is coordinated, indicates the presence of lattice water and that water present is not coordinated⁶.

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Polarographic Study of Tl(I)- α,α' -Bipyridyl System

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BIPYRIDYL complexes of Tl(I) in aqueous media have been reported using different analytical techniques^{1,2}. The effect of organic solvents on the polarographic behaviour of Tl(I) has been studied by Singh *et al*³. A survey of literature

reveals that the Tl(I)-bipyridyl system has not been studied polarographically in different aquo-organic media. The present communication presents the result of polarographic study of bipyridyl complexes of Tl(I) in aquo and 50% aquo-organic (dimethylformamide, ethyl acetate, ethanol and dioxane) media.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used. Solutions of Tl(I) and α,α' -bipyridyl were prepared in double distilled water. The test solutions containing $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Tl(I) and different concentrations of α,α' -bipyridyl were prepared in such a way that the DMF, dioxane, ethanol and ethyl acetate to water ratio in each case was 50% (v/v). Sodium perchlorate was used as supporting electrolyte ($\mu=1.0$) and gelatin (0.001%) as maximum suppressor.

Polarograms were recorded on a C.I.C. (Baroda), automatic pen recording polarograph. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution to remove the dissolved oxygen. The capillary had the following characteristics, $m=2.65 \text{ mg/sec}$, $t=3.0 \text{ sec}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.3 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$ (in 1.0 M NaClO₄, open circuit), $h_{0.01} = 35.0 \text{ cm}$. An Elico digital pH meter (model, L1-120) was used to measure the pH. All the observations were made at room temperature $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Hydrochloric acid/sodium hydroxide solutions were used to adjust the pH of the test solutions at 8.00, and the test solutions were deaerated with pure nitrogen gas.

Results and Discussion

In the presence of increasing concentrations (0.5×10^{-3} to $1 \times 10^{-3} M$) of α,α' -bipyridyl Tl(I) gave a well-defined one electron reduction wave at $\mu=1.0$ (NaClO₄) and pH 8.00 in aqueous and 50% aquo-organic media. The reduction of Tl(I) in presence of increasing concentration of α,α' -bipyridyl was found to be reversible in aqueous and aquo-organic media except for the ethyl acetate medium. The reduction of Tl(I) in ethyl acetate medium was reversible at low concentrations of the ligand while it tended to be of quasireversible nature with increasing ligand concentration. The $E_{1/2}$ for the quasireversible wave was calculated by Gellings⁴ method. In all the cases except for the ethyl acetate medium, the reduction was found to be diffusion controlled, which is apparent from the linear plots of the